

Meaning in Life buffers the association between risk factors for suicide and hopelessness in participants with mental disorders.

Abstract

Objective: Hopelessness is a proximal risk factor of suicide. Meaning in life has been found to be a protective factor against suicidal ideation; however, the majority of studies that have explored the role of meaning in life in the context of suicidality have been conducted in non-clinical populations. The aim of this study was to investigate whether meaning in life can moderate and buffer the association between suicide risk factors and hopelessness in a clinical sample with a heightened risk of suicide. Method: Two hundred and twenty-four participants diagnosed with mental disorders completed self-report measures of suicide risk factors, hopelessness and meaning in life. Results: The main result from this study was that meaning in life moderated the association between suicide risk factors and hopelessness. Conclusions: Meaning in life is an important variable in the prevention and treatment of people at risk of suicide.

Key words: meaning in life; hopelessness; suicide; buffer; moderation.

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Suicide rates have increased in the past few decades (Bertolote, & De Leo, 2012). They account for 1.4% of all deaths worldwide and are the 15th leading cause of death (Nock et al., 2012). Suffering from a severe mental disorder is a common factor leading to suicidal behavior. About 90% of people who commit suicide and 47–74% of the population at risk of suicide have a diagnosis of a mental disorder (Cavanagh, Carson, Sharpe, & Lawrie, 2003). About 24-33% of adolescents with psychiatric disorders report having made at least one suicide attempt during their lives (Asarnow et al., 2011), and 35–40% of clinical sample of adults report a history of suicide attempts (Claes et al., 2010). Research has identified various mental disorders as risk factors for suicide, including depression, anxiety, substance disorders (Nock et al., 2009; Vanderwerker et al., 2007), eating disorders (Chesney, Goodwin, & Fazel, 2014), borderline personality disorder (Schneider et al., 2008), bipolar disorder (Goodwin & Jamison, 2007) and psychotic disorders (Palmer, Pankratz, & Bostwick, 2005).

Studies have traditionally focused on identifying potential risk factors for suicide. Among the risk factors studied, hopelessness has been proposed as a proximal risk factor of suicide in several suicide theories (e.g., Beck, Steer, Kovacs, & Garrison, 1985; Joiner, 2005; Klonsky & May, 2015). Hopelessness is defined as negative expectations about the future that lead suicidal patients to believe that suicide is the only feasible strategy for dealing with their seemingly unsolvable problems (Beck, Weissman, Lester, & Trexler, 1974). Moreover, hopelessness has been found to be a predictor factor of eventual suicide (Beck, 2006; Brezo, Paris, & Turecki, 2006; Hawton, & van Heeringen, 2009), even when controlling for past suicidal behaviors (Klonsky, Kotov, Bakst, Rabinowitz, & Bromet, 2012). Additionally, research has found other factors strongly associated with the risk of suicide, such as previous suicide

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attempts, non-suicidal self-injury, depression, impulsivity, unemployment, living alone, low social support, or a family history of suicide attempts (Beautrais, 2004; Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009). However, the presence of risk factors does not fully explain suicidal behavior (Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009). Recently, research on suicide has focused on studying the variables that can act as buffers of suicidality (Johnson, Gooding, Wood, & Tarrrier, 2010; Osman et al., 2004), and several psychological variables have been found to be protective factors that create resilience to suicidality: attributional style (Hirsch, Wolford, LaLonde, Brunk, & Parker-Morris, 2009), problem-solving strategies (Grover et al., 2009), self-esteem (Tarrrier, Haddock, Lewis, Drake, & Gregg, 2006), sense of agency (Hobbs & McLaren, 2009), hopefulness (Meadows, Kaslow, Thompson, & Jurkovic, 2005), future orientation (Hirsch et al., 2006), reasons for living (Malone et al., 2000), and meaning in life (Marco, García-Alandete, Pérez, & Botella, 2014; Kleiman & Beaver, 2013).

Meaning in life is a basic construct of the human condition and a core facet of the Positive Psychology movement (Schulenberg & Melton, 2010). There are numerous definitions of meaning in life, including coherence in life and sense of fulfillment, self-actualization, goal directedness, sense of purpose and authentic living, so that meaning and purpose can be used interchangeably (Przepiorka, 2012). Meaning in life is related to the experience of freedom, responsibility, self-determination, a positive view of life, the future and oneself, purpose and the accomplishment of existential goals, coping, satisfaction with life and self-realization, and having a strong sense of purpose in life (Frankl, 2006; García-Alandete, Gallego-Pérez, & Pérez-Delgado, 2009). Meaning in life is composed of two main dimensions (García-Alandete, Rosa, & Sellés, 2013): a) Satisfaction and Meaning in Life, which is the cognitive component of meaning of life

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in terms of satisfaction and fulfillment, representing the retrospective dimension of meaning of life; and b) Life Goals and Purposes, which is the motivational component of meaning of life, related to setting vital goals and purposes and representing the prospective dimension of meaning of life.

A high level of meaning in life is positively associated with mental health and psychological well-being (e.g., Ho, Cheung & Cheung, 2010; Kleftaras & Psarra, 2012). By contrast, a low level of meaning in life is a negative cognitive-emotional-motivational state associated with hopelessness, a perception of lack of control over one's life, and the absence of vital goals. Low meaning in life has been found to be associated with depression (Psarra & Kleftaras, 2013; Volkert, Schulz, Brütt, & Andreas, 2014), hopelessness (García-Alandete et al., 2009), and suicide (Edwards & Holden, 2003), among other mental health problems, in a large number of studies (e.g. Mascaro & Rosen, 2005). In the same way, meaning in life has been found to be a protective factor against suicidal ideation (Kleiman & Beaver, 2013) and psychopathology (Schulenberg, Strack, & Buchanan, 2011).

Most of the studies mentioned above explored the role of meaning in life in the context of suicidality in non-clinical populations (e.g. Kleiman & Beaver, 2013). To our knowledge, only two studies have analyzed the role of meaning in life as a resilience factor against suicide in a clinical sample. In 49 patients with mental disorders, Heisel and Flett (2004) found that the degree of perception of purpose in life moderated the association between depression and suicide ideation. Marco et al. (2014) found that meaning in life mediated the relationship between depression and hopelessness in a sample of 80 participants diagnosed with borderline personality

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disorder. Thus, it would be necessary to extend the research in this area of knowledge using clinical samples.

The present study contributes to the literature in two ways. On the one hand, it is the first study to explore whether meaning in life could moderate and buffer the association between distal risk factors for suicide and hopelessness, a proximal suicide risk factor, in a clinical sample composed of participants with mental disorders. We hypothesize that meaning in life moderates the relationship between suicide risk factors and hopelessness. That is, for individuals with high meaning in life, there would be a weaker relationship between suicide risk factors and hopelessness, compared to individuals with low meaning in life. On the other hand, the other aim of the current study is to investigate whether the two dimensions of meaning in life -Satisfaction and Meaning in Life or Life Goals and Purposes- may play equal roles as buffers against hopelessness. These two dimensions have been studied in non-clinical populations; for this reason, it is necessary to analyze the individual buffering effects of the dimensions of meaning in life in a clinical population. We hypothesize that both Satisfaction and Meaning in Life, and Life Goals and Purposes moderate the relationships between suicide risk factors and hopelessness. Additionally, examining the hypotheses in clinical samples outside of the United States would lead to increased knowledge about suicide risk and protective factors in European countries.

Method

Participants

The sample was recruited from the outpatient unit of six public mental health clinics in Spain. Participants were consecutively recruited from January to December 2014. Participants were included in the study if they met criteria for a mental disorder

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according to DSM-IV-TR criteria (APA, 2000) and were between 13 and 70 years old. The exclusion criterion was moderate or severe mental retardation. Participants were white Europeans, and all of them understood Spanish. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was given by participants, and no compensation was offered to them. Ethical approval for carrying out this study was granted by the Hospital Ethics Committee.

The final sample comprised 224 participants, 85.7% ($n = 192$) women and 14.3% ($n = 32$) men. The majority of the participants, 55.3% ($n = 124$), met the criteria for eating disorders, 12.1% ($n = 27$) for anxiety disorders, 10.7% ($n = 24$) for major depression disorder, 8.9% ($n = 20$) for schizophrenia, 7.6% ($n = 17$) for substance dependence disorder, and 5.4% ($n = 12$) for borderline personality disorder; 55.5% ($n = 124$) of the participants had attempted suicide at some time in their lives. Participants' age range was broad: 13-68 years old with an average age of 34.38 ($SD = 12.24$). In the sample, 8.3% of the participants were between 13 and 18 years old, 47% were between 18 and 35 years old, 38.2% were between 35 and 55 years old, and finally, 6.5% were between 55 and 70 years old. The duration of the diagnosis was 1-35 years, with an average of 12.71 years ($SD = 7.63$). The range on the Global Assessment Functioning Scale of the DSM-IV was from 30 to 87, with an average of 52.89 ($SD = 9.88$).

As for the participants' educational level, 2.8% ($n = 6$) had no studies, 27.8% ($n = 62$) had primary school education, 35.4% ($n = 80$) had high school education, and 34% ($n = 76$) had university studies. Regarding occupation, 25% ($n = 56$) were employed, and 75% ($n = 168$) were unemployed.

Assessments and measures

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Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Axis I Disorders (SCID I; First, Spitzer, Gibbon, & Williams, 2002). This is an interview for the major DSM-IV-TR (APA, 2000) Axis I diagnoses. It is widely used in mental health and offers good psychometric properties; the Kappa range is .66-.83, demonstrating reliability (Lobbestael, Leurgans, & Arntz, 2011).

Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Axis II Personality Disorders (SCID II; First, Gibbon, Spitzer, Williams, & Benjamin (1997). This is an interview for DSM-IV-TR (APA, 2000) Axis II Personality Disorder diagnoses. It includes 119 questions and has a Kappa of .74, demonstrating reliability for admitted patients (First et al., 1997).

Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS; Beck et al., 1974). This is a twenty-item dichotomous (true-false) scale designed to assess current negative expectations about the future (e.g., from the previous two weeks). Level of hopelessness is a predictive factor of eventual suicide in the clinical population (Beck, 2006). The scale was validated in the Spanish population (Viñas et al., 2004). For our data, the internal consistency for the total score was adequate, $\alpha = .92$.

Suicide Risk Scale (SRS; Plutchik, Van Praag, Conte, & Picard, 1989). It is a self-report questionnaire that assesses significant predictors of suicidal behavior, or suicide risk factors. The SRS assesses lifelong symptoms, including patients' past history of suicide attempts ("Have you ever attempted suicide?"), family history of suicide attempts ("Has anyone in your family ever tried to commit suicide?"), suicidal ideation ("Have you ever thought about committing suicide?"), aggressiveness, impulsivity, feelings of worthlessness, and present states often associated with suicidal patients (Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009): Feelings of Depression, hopelessness,

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insomnia, interest in relationships with others, and if the patient is divorced or widowed. It discriminates between patients who have attempted suicide and those who have not. It consists of 15 dichotomous items (yes/no). The purpose of the SRS is not to predict future suicides, but rather the risk of suicide attempts. The logic of this approach is that many suicide attempters or suicides have made a suicide attempt in the past, so this scale makes it possible to identify suicide attempters (Plutchik et al., 1989). The cut-off point indicating substantial suicide risk is established at 6 points in the Spanish validated version (Rubio et al., 1988). The Spanish version's reliability was $\alpha = .90$ (Rubio et al., 1988) and showed adequate reliability in our data, $\alpha = .95$.

Purpose in Life-10 (PIL-10) (García-Alandete et al., 2013). This scale is a reduced version of the PIL (Crumbaugh & Maholick, 1969). It consists of a 10-item Likert scale (7 levels of response) related to different aspects of meaning in life: (1) enthusiasm vs. boredom, (2) excitement in living, (3) presence of clear life goals, (4) newness of each day, (5) wishing for more lives, (6) activity after retirement, (7) good things in life, (8) having a reason to be alive, (9) capacity to find meaning, (10) presence of goals/life purpose. The total score ranges from 10 to 70, and higher scores indicate greater meaning in life. The PIL-10 includes two dimensions: Satisfaction and Meaning in Life, and b) Life Goals and Purposes.

The PIL-10 offered good psychometric properties and high reliability for the global scale ($\alpha = .85$), for the Satisfaction and Meaning in Life subscale ($\alpha = .84$), and for the Life Goals and Purposes subscale ($\alpha = .69$) (García-Alandete, 2014). In our sample, there was adequate internal consistency for the PIL-10 ($\alpha = .91$), for Satisfaction and meaning in life ($\alpha = .87$), and for Life goals and purposes ($\alpha = .83$).

Procedure

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First, we contacted with ten mental health services specialized in eating disorders, psychotic disorders and mood disorders, and we explained the aim of the study and asked if they were interested in collaborating in this research. Six services, 60% of all the services contacted, decided to collaborate in this study. Four services specialized in eating disorders, one specialized in general mental health, and one specialized in psychotic disorders. Then, 240 participants were asked if they wanted to collaborate in the research. Nine refused to participate in the research, and seven of those who accepted did not fill out the questionnaires. Three individual assessment sessions were conducted during 2 consecutive weeks. All the assessment sessions were conducted by clinical psychologists with more than 10 years of experience in clinical psychology. In the first session, we explained the aim of the study, and we asked if they were interested in collaborating in the study. In the second session, the diagnosis of mental disorders was established using the SCID-I (First et al., 2002) and the diagnosis of personality disorders with the SCID-II (First et al., 1997). In the third session, the participants filled out the questionnaires.

Statistical procedure

Prior to the analysis, taking into account that the SRS (Plutchik et al., 1989) assesses significant predictors of suicidal behavior and item 7 assesses hopelessness ("I see the future without hope"), we decided to eliminate item 7 to reduce potential confusion between the measures. First, correlation analyses were carried out between the key variables. Second, a hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to examine whether meaning in life measured by the PIL-10 moderated the association between risk factors of suicide measured by the SRS and hopelessness measured by the BHS. In the first step of this analysis, the covariates age and gender were entered into the regression

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model. In the second step, hopelessness (BHS) and suicide risk factors (SRS) were entered. In the third step, meaning in life (PIL-10) scores were entered. In the fourth step, the interaction term between suicide risk factors (SRS) and meaning in life (PIL-10) was entered. In each step, standardized variables were used to avoid multicollinearity (Frazier, Tix, & Barron, 2004). If the addition of the interaction term in the fourth step added significant predictive variance to the regression model, this indicated a moderating effect of meaning in life (PIL-10) in the association between suicide risk factors (SRS) and hopelessness (BHS) (Cohen & Cohen, 1983; Frazier et al., 2004). These analyses were then repeated with the subscales of the PIL-10: Satisfaction and Meaning in Life, and Life Goals and Purposes. Data were analyzed using SPSS 20 (SPSS, Chicago, IL).”

Results

Zero-order correlations, means and standard deviations for the variables are displayed in Table 1. Results showed that risk factors for suicide assessed with the SRS were highly correlated with hopelessness (BHS). Similarly, meaning in life, according to the global score on the PIL-10 and the scores on the Satisfaction and Meaning in Life and Life Goals and Purposes subscales, were found to be moderately and inversely correlated with hopelessness. There were no correlations between risk factors for suicide (SRS) and the global score on the PIL-10 or with the subscales satisfaction and meaning in life, and life goals and purposes.

As Table 2 shows, meaning in life measured with the PIL-10 moderated the association between suicide risk factors (SRS) and hopelessness (BHS) when age and gender were controlled. Once suicide risk factor scores (SRS) were entered, meaning in life (PIL-10) predicted hopelessness, both in addition to suicide risk factors (SRS), $\beta=-$

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3.18, and when interacting with suicide risk factors (SRS), $\beta=-1.28$, thus supporting a moderating impact of meaning in life (PIL-10) in the association between suicide risk factors (SRS) and hopelessness (BHS). This result suggest that for those patients with high levels of meaning in life (PIL-10), increased suicide risk factors (SRS) corresponded to lower increases in hopelessness (BHS) than in the patients with low meaning in life. Next, each of the PIL-10 subscales was examined as a moderator of the association between suicide risk factors (SRS) and hopelessness (BHS) when age and gender were controlled. A significant moderating impact was found for the subscale of Satisfaction and Meaning in Life, which predicted hopelessness (BHS), both in addition to suicide risk factors (SRS), $\beta =-3.26$, and interactively with suicide risk factors (SRS) $\beta = -1.43$. In the same way, a significant moderator effect was found for the subscale of Life Goals and Purposes, which predicted hopelessness (BHS) both in addition to suicide risk factors (SRS), $\beta=-1.40$, and interactively with suicide risk factors $\beta=-2.67$.

Discussion

The main aim of this study was to determine whether meaning in life moderates and buffers the relationship between distal suicide risk factors and hopelessness, a proximal suicide risk factor, in a clinical sample. The sample recruited for this study had the main suicide risk factors: Diagnosis of a psychiatric disorder, high levels of hopelessness (Beck et al., 1974), elevated number of suicide risk factors assessed with the SRS (Plutchik et al., 1989), a large number had attempted suicide in the past (Hawton & van Heeringen, 2009), and low meaning in life (Mascaro & Rosen, 2005). The main results of this study show that meaning in life, assessed with the PIL-10 (García-Alandete et al., 2013), moderated the association between distal suicide risk factors and hopelessness, a proximal suicide risk factor, in a clinical sample. The second

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aim of the current study was to investigate whether the two dimensions of meaning in life, Satisfaction and Meaning in Life or Life Goals and Purposes, might buffer against hopelessness equally. The results indicated that both PIL-10 dimensions buffered the association between suicide risk factors and hopelessness in our clinical sample. Thus, the results of this study suggest that meaning in life could act as a moderating factor against hopelessness in a clinical sample with a high risk of suicide.

Although this is the first study to investigate this buffering hypothesis in a clinical sample, our findings are consistent with previous results indicating a negative association between meaning in life and risk of suicide in non-clinical (Edwards & Holden, 2003; Hunter & O'Connor, 2003; Kleiman, Adams, Kashdan, & Riskind, 2013; Kleiman & Beaver, 2013) and clinical populations (Heisel & Flett, 2004). The results of the present study support those found by Marco et al. (2014), who showed that meaning in life mediated, and therefore helped to explain, the relationship between depression and hopelessness in a sample composed of participants with borderline personality disorder with severe suicide risk.

We want to emphasize that the majority of the participants, 55.3% ($n = 124$), met the criteria for eating disorders. Eating disorders are associated with an elevated risk of suicide, mainly in bulimia nervosa (e.g. Smith et al., 2015) and anorexia nervosa (Chesney et al., 2014). Therefore, these results suggest that meaning in life could buffer the relationship between suicide risk factors and hopelessness in a sample composed mainly of eating disorders. We want to highlight that this is the first study to examine meaning in life in participants diagnosed with eating disorders, and future studies need to confirm this partial result and explore whether meaning in life is associated with the

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main psychopathology of eating disorders, including body image, emotional dysregulation, dieting or perfectionism.

These findings highlight the importance of identifying the variables that buffer specific suicide risk factors because this will allow us to develop psychotherapeutic interventions aimed to strengthen these buffering factors. The results of the present study suggest that meaning in life could produce resilience to suicide through a specific risk factor: Hopelessness. We chose hopelessness to assess suicidality because Hopelessness is a variable that has been proposed as an important proximal risk factor of suicide in several suicide theories (e.g., Beck et al., 1985; Klonsky & May, 2015; Joiner, 2005). Moreover, several studies have shown that it is an important predictor factor of suicide (e.g. Beck, 2006; Brezo et al., 2006; Hawton, & van Heeringen, 2009; Klonsky et al., 2012).

These results agree with current theories of suicide behavior. The biosocial developmental model of Borderline Personality Disorder (BDP) (Linehan, 2015) suggests that emotional dysregulation developed in invalidating environments will result in an inability to regulate emotions and interfere with the development and maintenance of the self. This leads to an intolerable experience of self and a feeling that impels the individual to seek escape – in the case of BPD through suicide, self-harm, substance abuse or other self-destructive behaviors. Several studies indicate that low meaning in life is associated with emotional dysregulation (Abeyta, Routledge, Juhl, & Robinson, 2015), negative affect and emotions (Keyes, Shmotkin, & Ryff, 2002), anxiety (Mascaro & Rosen, 2005), upbringing in an invalidating environment (Bearsley & Cummins, 1999), hostility, anti-sociality and aggression (Mascaro et al., 2004), and hopelessness (Marco et al., 2014). From this perspective, several mental disorders can

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be conceptualized as emotion-regulation disorders (e.g. depression, substance abuse, anxiety disorders, etc.). In this model, a main construct is the “wise mind”, which is closely related to meaning in life. Other theories, such as the Three-Step Theory of suicide (Klonsky & May, 2015), state that hopelessness is a proximal factor for suicide ideation, and that the combination of pain and hopelessness is necessary to bring about suicidal ideation. Moreover, in the second step of the theory (Klonsky & May, 2015), the authors state that disrupted connectedness is necessary to continue with the future suicide attempt. Connectedness refers to one’s attachment to a job, project, role, interest, or any sense of perceived purpose or meaning that keeps one invested in living. This concept is similar to meaning in life, and the authors also suggest that connectedness can be a protective factor. Moreover, Klonsky and May (2015) suggest that disrupted connectedness is similar to low belongingness and high burdensomeness, two main variables in Joiner’s Interpersonal Psychological Theory of Suicide (Joiner 2005). This theory states that suicidal ideation is increased by feelings of low belongingness and high burdensomeness, with hopelessness about these feelings. Thus, future studies should explore the association between meaning in life and feelings of belongingness and burdensomeness in participants at risk of suicide.

The results of this study suggest that psychotherapeutic interventions aimed at developing meaning in life could act as protective factors against suicide risk. Specifically, psychotherapeutic interventions should be focused on increasing the two dimensions of meaning in life: Satisfaction and Meaning in Life, the retrospective dimension of meaning of life, and Life Goals and Purposes, the prospective dimension of meaning in life. Thus, this study supports the application of therapies focused on vital values, such as: a) Dialectical Behavioral Therapy (DBT) (Linehan, 1993), which

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provides new skills for emotional regulation and teaches patients to identify or change the core values in their lives and subsequently create a life worth living. The DBT has been shown to be effective in treating patients diagnosed with BPD with suicide attempts and self-harm (Cameron, Reed, & Gaudiano, 2014; Carmel, Comtois, Harned, Holler, & McFarr, 2015; Linehan et al., 2006); b) Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) (Hayes, Luoma, Bond, Masuda, & Lillis, 2006), which uses a variety of exercises to help a client choose life directions in various domains (e.g. family, career, spirituality) while undermining verbal processes that might lead to choices based on avoidance or social compliance. In ACT the acceptance strategies or “being present” are the path to a more vital, values-consistent life. ACT has been shown to be effective in treating anxiety disorders, depression, addiction, and somatic health problems (Davis, Morina, Powers, Smits, & Emmelkamp, 2015); c) Meaning Centered Counseling and Therapy (MCCT) (Wong, 1999). The MCCT has elaborated and enhanced the classic logotherapy by Frankl (2006), introducing new constructs and skills consistent with logotherapy. Lapierre, Dubé, Bouffard, & Alain (2007) found that psychotherapeutic interventions aimed at increasing meaning in life helped patients to establish, plan, pursue, and realize meaningful concrete personal goals, leading to decreased depression, psychological distress and suicide risk.

This study presents some limitations that should be emphasized. First, it is a cross-sectional study, which means we cannot talk about causality between variables.

Therefore, future research should replicate this study using a longitudinal design.

Second, the sample, although large, was not formed of groups of mental disorders with similar sizes, which would have allowed us to analyze differences between groups.

However, the sample comes from several different public mental health institutions, and

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participants had major suicide risk factors. As the inclusion criteria were very broad, it is reasonable to state that the sample is representative of patients seen in daily clinical practice. Third, our sample was composed primarily of women, which limits generalizability to men. In the future, researchers could replicate our findings in a sample with a similar proportion of men and women. Fourth, psychiatric co-morbidity was not established, and so future studies will have to replicate this research and include the co-morbidity of the participants, which will allow us to analyze whether the participants with low meaning in life could have more psychiatric co-morbidity than the participants with high meaning in life. Finally, another limitation is that the participants were recruited from mental health services in Spain, and so the sample may not be representative of other cultures, e.g. United States or Asian countries. Thus, the results may not be transferable to other countries. For this reason, future studies should use representative sampling from different countries.

Additionally, the results of this study suggest that future research should address whether adding a specific treatment component focused on meaning in life within the context of the usual treatment for people with high risk of suicide (e.g. borderline personality disorders, major depression, suicide attempters or people with high scores on hopelessness) could increase its efficacy in reducing the risk of suicide. Moreover, in future research it would be particularly helpful to examine whether the buffering role of meaning in life might have different effects in different age groups, for example adolescents, young adults or elderly people, within the framework of a developmental perspective.

In conclusion, the current study found that high meaning in life could buffer the pernicious impact of suicidal risk factors in the development of hopelessness in a

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sample of participants with mental disorders and a high risk of suicide. These results suggest that meaning in life could be an important variable for further research in suicide risk prevention and intervention.

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